

Design and Fabrication of Material Handling Trolley for Building Construction

Abhishek¹, Abhishek J Paul², Abhishek Reddy G³, Dileep⁴, Pavan D⁵

^{1,2,3,4} Student, REVA University, India

⁵ Assistant Professor, REVA University, India

Abstract

Human effort in labor involves physical and mental exertion to perform tasks, often contributing to the production of goods or services. The intensity and nature of labor can vary from manual tasks, all requiring dedication and skill. This project aims at developing a mechanism for easy transportation of heavy loads over stairs. The need for such system arises from day-to-day requirements in our society. The trolley can easily ascend and descend on the stairways, in which the human effort can be minimum, and the load can be moved from one place to another place even on the stairways.

Keywords: Stair climbing, Trolley, Belt drive, Human Effort.

1. INTRODUCTION

A trolley is a small vehicle with wheels that can be pushed or pulled along and is used for carrying things. A stair climbing trolley is a type of trolley fitted with rotating wheels or tracks so that it can be pushed, pulled up or down on a stairway. Stair climbing trolley can be manual or battery-powered and, are commonly found in wheel, track, and push arm. When used properly, trolleys can protect people from back injuries and other health problems that can result from lifting heavy loads.

An ordinary hand trolley is which includes tri wheels placed at the bottom of trolley. The two handles are furnished to help the frame and applied the human attempt, handles are used to push or pull the trolley. At some imprecise point in the distant past humankind discovered that certain rocks now called ores could be smelted, producing metal. Further, they discovered that the metal product was malleable and ductile and thus able to be formed into various tools, adornments and put to other practical uses.

This project introduces a new option to transportation of loads over the staircase. The trolley is designed in such a way that slides on staircase with the help of belt drive.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Kunal Dhall et.al [1] : The design of wheel chair is done semi-automatic because to reduce the manufacturing cost to high extend so a lower class people also afford that and make the life easy and can easily use the wheel chair on stairs. For lifting up wheelchair a back arm is given which operate with the help of dc motors and the movement of arm is manual it's done at 45 degree when use for stairs climbing. The frame of the chair is made up of iron and wood and covers with fabric and form.

Md. A. Hossain et.al [2] : During the test run of this project, it was realized that it would be capable of carrying heavy load without suffering any deformation or local fractures if it would go into real world production at an ideal scale. Though the initial cost of the project seemed to be higher but more accurate manufacturing would shorten this.

Yash Mali et.al [3] : This project aims at developing a mechanism for easy transportation of heavy loads over stairs. The need for such a system arises from day-to-day requirements in our society. Devices such as hand trolleys are used to relieve the stress of lifting while on flat ground; however this devices usually fails when it comes to carrying the load over short fleet of stairs. In the light of this, the project attempts to design a stair climbing hand cart which can carry heavy objects up the stairs with less effort compared to carrying them manually.

Prof. M.P. Sathe et.al [4] : The planning is created terribly safe and there's no likelihood of failure of the frame and wheels beneath traditional condition. According to the tests conducted, the support ascent tram encompasses a capability of carrying a load of 100kgs on flat surface. It's the flexibility to ascend a flight of stairs of 45-degree elevation carrying a weight of 40kgs. The main good thing about the project is support ascent mechanism for load carrier with decreasing effort. Doing higher work with lesser effort has been the most objectives of kinsmen in any field.

Kartik S Naragund et.al [5] : The project resulted in the creation of a functional prototype that effectively addresses the mobility challenges faced by individuals with limited mobility. The mobile stair lift demonstrated its ability to climb stairs, function as a wheelchair, and seamlessly transform into a trolley, showcasing its versatility and practicality.

Snehita Kilari et.al [6] : The primary objective of bearing heavy load like 120-150 kg is achieved during testing. The performance is slightly complicated when the straight frame was tested for varying step sizes. But when tested with Quasi-static frame, the vehicle exhibited greater performance even for stairs with different dimensions. Static structural analysis demonstrates that it is capable of moving heavy loads with less deformation and without any fracture.

Shamiuzzaman Akhtar et.al [7] : This article deals with the designing and manufacturing of a vehicle, which can climb stair or move along very rough surface. The technical issues in designing of this vehicle are the stability and speed of the vehicle while climbing stairs. However, the steepness of the stairs is also the important concern of this study. The uses of this special vehicle are in the frequent lift of goods such as books for library, medicines for hospital, regular mails for any institutes, or transportation any toxic material for industries and give freedom to the retarded person or paralyzed patients to move anywhere over flat surface as well as stairs.

3. OBJECTIVES

1. The trolley should handle the pay load of the material between 20kg to 50kg.
2. The trolley should ascend and descend along the stairways with the full pay load of the material.
3. The trolley should weigh the pay load of the materials and also the battery consumption digitally.

4. METHODOLOGY

Based on the research of previous studies and existing technologies, the belt driven material handling trolley was chosen as primary mechanism for our project. The selection of material was made based on the model development using Fusion 360 software. The testing of trolley was conducted under different conditions on different staircases.

5. WORKING PRINCIPLE

FIGURE 1: Working Principle

Here the working principle of material handling is as shown in the above fig. In which it consists of a power input as a direct current, motor, and the belt drives connected to the motor with the help of shafts.

When the power is supplied to the motor, it starts to rotate which in turn make the belt drive to rotate. The belt drive is made to incline at an angle which makes it contact with the staircase, the inter-locking system helps to withstand the inclination on application of load. Belt drive is designed in such a way that it keeps a edge contact with at least 3 stairs which makes it a smooth movement.

Components and Description:

The working of Material handling trolley consists of the following components to full fill the requirements of complete operation of the machine.

Main frame:

Main frame is a steel structure which support and carry the components mounted on the frame. Material used for the construction of the frame is mild steel as it can easily cut, bend and weld into required shape without specialized tools.

Figure 2: Main frame

DC motor:

A DC motor is an electrical motor that uses direct current (DC) to produce mechanical force. The most common types rely on magnetic forces produced by currents in the coils. Nearly all types of DC motors have some internal mechanism, either electromechanical or electronic, to periodically change the direction of current in part of the motor.

Figure 3: DC motor

Battery:

An electric battery is a source of electric power consisting of one or more electrochemical cells with external connections for powering electrical devices. When a battery is supplying power, its positive terminal is the cathode and its negative terminal is the anode.

Figure 4: Battery

Belt drive:

A belt drive is a mechanical system that uses an flat belt and rollers to transmit power between two or more rotating shafts.

Figure 5: Belt drive

Load sensors:

Load sensors, also known as load cells, are electronic devices that convert compression and tension forces into an electrical signal. They are often used to determine the weight of an object, such as in industrial or household scales.

Figure 6: Load sensor

6. DESIGN

Design Calculations:

Motor selection:

Mass = 20kg

Speed of motor = 10rpm

Pulley on the motor = 0.14m

Force under gravity:

Force = mass * acceleration

Force = 20 * 9.81

Force = 196 N

Force under acceleration:

Force = mass * acceleration

Force = 20 * 0.157

Force = 3.14 N

Torque = Force * Radius of wheel

Torque = 199.14 * 0.15

Torque = 29.871 Nm

Frame:

Material used in frame = Mild steel

Length of frame = 580mm

Width of frame = 500mm

Height of frame = 1240mm

Figure 7: Frame design

Figure 8: Belt drive design

Load sensor

Rated load = 40kg

Precision = 0.02

Track belt

Tooth Height = 1.27mm

Tooth Type = Trapezoid

Belt Thickness = 2.3mm

Figure 9: Assembly design

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing of Material handling trolley has been done and it was able to carry the load and slide over different staircase under all conditions. It can slide over the flat surface uniformly and also on the staircase with the rated speed of 10rpm uniformly while carrying load.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Design and Development of Material Handling trolley had some limitations as it was a first step. During the test the trolley was able to satisfy all the results and carry load in all conditions. It can handle real time applications based on required field.

9. REFERENCES

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